

Light-Based IoT-Enabled Battery-Free Active Product Monitoring for Sustainable Smart Packaging Applications

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Abstract

Product wastage due to inadequate condition monitoring during storage and transport remains a significant challenge in modern supply chains, particularly for perishable goods. Conventional packaging systems often lack real-time visibility and rely on battery-powered electronics, which pose sustainability and scalability issues. To address these limitations, this work presents a sustainable smart packaging system based on Light-based Internet of Things (LIoT) architecture, termed LIoT-based Active Smart Packaging (LIoT-ASP). The proposed solution integrates Photovoltaic Energy Harvesting (PV-EH) and Optical Wireless Communication (OWC) to enable battery-free, energy-autonomous operation for product condition monitoring in retail and logistics environments. A prototype system was developed using commercially available components, incorporating both visible light downlink and infrared uplink channels based on consumer device IR protocol-inspired OWC, adapted for low-power operation. The bidirectional OWC supports a data rate of 1.1 kbps, sufficient for periodic sensing and display updates in low-throughput smart packaging applications. The system employs energy-aware control mechanisms and intermittent operation strategies to manage sensing and data communication under variable indoor illumination. Performance of the LIoT-ASP concept was assessed through the developed proof-of-concept prototype system, followed by experimental validation in a real-world scenario involving temperature-sensitive dairy products. The

system successfully detected and reported threshold violations via cloud-connected mobile alerts, demonstrating reliable end-to-end functionality. These findings validate the practical feasibility of deploying LIoT-ASP systems as a sustainable and scalable solution for smart packaging applications.

Light-based IoT, Smart packaging, Optical wireless communication, Energy harvesting, Battery-free IoT, Visible light communication, Sustainable wireless communications.

1 Introduction

With the advancement of 6G and next-generation communication technologies, sustainability has emerged as a fundamental Key Performance Indicator (KPI) for future Internet of Things (IoT) systems [1]. In this context, IoT sensor networks play a pivotal role by facilitating real-time monitoring and accurate data acquisition, which are essential for achieving environmental sustainability objectives across diverse application domains [2].

In the domain of food and consumer goods, storage and packaging are critical for maintaining product quality within acceptable parameters throughout the entire life cycle, while also supporting marketing functions. Traditional packaging methods typically rely on static expiration dates, providing only approximate estimations of product condition. This absence of dynamic, real-time information may expose consumers to food-borne illnesses due to the consumption of unsafe or degraded products [3]. In order to address these limitations, concepts of active and intelligent food packaging have been proposed, with legal and safety concerns gradually being assessed and standardized over time [4, 5].

Smart packaging employs IoT technologies by incorporating sensors such as Time-Temperature Indi-

cators (TTIs) and gas sensors to enable real-time monitoring, traceability, and enhanced safety features. These sensors facilitate interactive feedback mechanisms that dynamically communicate the product’s condition through the packaging interface [6, 7]. As a result, intelligent systems are being developed to continuously monitor and report product status during storage and transport. These advancements are essential in addressing critical challenges related to product integrity, consumer safety, and waste minimization across sectors handling temperature- or condition-sensitive goods. Particularly in food and pharmaceutical applications, modern packaging increasingly integrates biosensors, freshness indicators, and real-time traceability platforms to enhance supply chain transparency and reduce environmental impact [6, 8].

However, the majority of IoT-enabled smart packaging solutions currently rely on Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID) technologies, including battery-free passive tags, battery-assisted semi-passive tags, and fully active battery-powered RFID systems [9–11]. In large-scale RFID deployments, the omnidirectional nature of Radio Frequency (RF) communication can cause reader collisions, where overlapping reader signals lead to interference, increased latency, and tag misreads, thereby demanding additional coordination mechanisms and increasing system complexity to mitigate these issues [12]. While widely used for identification and tracking, passive RFID devices are generally limited to single-function operation and lack support for continuous sensing or autonomous functionality. Battery-powered variants, although capable of active sensing, may perform sub-optimally in environments where low temperatures affect battery efficiency and reliability [13]. A more significant concern is their limited sustainability, as these systems require periodic battery replacement or maintenance [11]. This dependence introduces substantial challenges for large-scale consumer product applications due to sustainability concerns linked with electrochemical energy storage. The widespread use of batteries imposes considerable environmental and economic burdens, including high energy consumption associated with raw material extraction, manufacturing, transportation, and end-of-life recycling. Consequently, battery-reliant designs counteract the very sustainability objectives that smart packaging seeks to support [14].

Meanwhile, the development of energy autonomy

in IoT systems has inspired the development of Light-based IoT (LIoT) architectures, which utilize indoor illumination for both Photovoltaic based Energy Harvesting (PV-EH) and Optical Wireless Communication (OWC) [15–17]. These systems are particularly applicable to settings with existing illumination infrastructure, such as supermarkets, cold chains, and storage facilities, which are common environments for smart packaging deployment. By harvesting indoor light, LIoT designs eliminate the need for electrochemical batteries, thereby enabling zero-maintenance operation and advancing sustainability goals. Furthermore, OWC enables communication over the unlicensed optical spectrum, offering advantages such as physical-layer security and immunity to electromagnetic interference [15]. These benefits are particularly valuable in high-density environments where conventional RF communication may encounter interference and spectrum congestion. The integration of OWC into smart packaging supports reliable and interference-resilient communication in such large-scale applications. In addition, the hybrid integration of conventional electronics with sustainable technologies such as printed electronics further enhances ecological performance. Printed components, compatible with low-cost and energy-efficient fabrication techniques, are especially suitable for large-area or flexible modules in smart packaging nodes [15]. This combination supports scalability and aligns with the principles of circular and sustainable product design [18].

This research builds upon earlier work [15–17], which established the foundational concept and feasibility of LIoT for energy-autonomous communication. The present study advances this foundation by integrating a battery-free LIoT architecture with active smart packaging functionality, resulting in a sustainable and optically communicating packaging solution, referred to as LIoT-based Active Smart Packaging (LIoT-ASP). Specifically, this work extends previously proposed LIoT designs [16, 17] from component-level feasibility studies to a fully integrated end-to-end smart packaging system that includes application based validation, real-time monitoring, and cloud connectivity. The key contributions of this work are as follows:

- Develops a battery-free LIoT-ASP system that integrates PV-EH, OWC, and energy aware intermittent operation strategy, enabling dynamic task scheduling and cloud connectivity under

variable indoor illumination.

- Validates system performance in a cold-chain use case with temperature-sensitive goods, demonstrating autonomous sensing, robust IR-based uplink, and flicker-safe VLC compliant with standards, building on established IR protocols and LIoT design frameworks.

The remainder of the article is organized as follows: Section II introduces the proposed system model; Section III discusses the design considerations and implementation challenges; Section IV details the prototype implementation used for evaluation; Section V presents the performance evaluation; and Section VI concludes the paper.

2 System Model

Designing sustainable IoT systems for indoor environments requires a careful balance between energy availability, communication efficiency, and compact system integration. LIoT offers a compelling solution in this context by combining PV-EH with OWC, particularly using VLC for downlink communication. This dual-purpose approach enables energy-autonomous operation while simultaneously exploiting existing illumination infrastructure for data communication [15–17]. A key consideration in the design of indoor LIoT systems is the evaluation of available energy sources and the identification of low-power communication technologies compatible with indoor optical channels. Commonly deployed white LED luminaires, originally intended for general illumination, typically offer modulation bandwidths in the range of 3 to 5 MHz, making them suitable for supporting low-data-rate VLC [19]. These data rates are sufficient for applications such as smart packaging and environmental monitoring, where sensing updates are periodic and data payloads are minimal. In such scenarios, parameters such as temperature, humidity, or spoilage indicators can be transmitted intermittently without requiring continuous throughput. With the global adoption rate of LED-based lighting projected to exceed 90% by 2030 [20], this widespread infrastructure presents a promising opportunity to repurpose existing luminaires as Optical Access Points (OAP) within the LIoT framework [15–17]. Utilizing the same lighting infrastructure for both illumination and communication reduces hardware redundancy and supports sustainability goals by maximiz-

ing the utility of already-installed components, aligning with the environmental requirements of next-generation battery-free smart packaging systems.

The distributed LIoT nodes in such systems must be capable of performing sensing, OWC, and PV-EH under intermittent and variable illumination conditions. Their design aligns conceptually with the “Smart Dust” vision [21], which envisions ultra-miniaturized autonomous devices that integrate sensing, power management, communication, and computation within a highly constrained physical footprint. In applications such as active smart packaging, where compact form factor, energy autonomy, and intermittent updates are critical, these nodes must adhere to zero-energy operation principles. This includes the use of PV-EH modules, energy-aware optical transceivers, and ultra-low-power sensors. The integration of these components enables sustained operation despite fluctuations in indoor light availability and supports intermittent computing when energy resources are insufficient for continuous operation.

In order to ensure scalability and deployment practicality, LIoT-ASP node design must also prioritize compactness, cost-efficiency, and environmental compatibility. The use of recyclable materials, printed electronics, and efficient energy conversion interfaces contributes to reducing environmental impact without compromising device capability [15]. In the context of active smart packaging, such considerations are vital for achieving high-volume deployment with minimal ecological footprint. At the system level, the proposed LIoT architecture consists of a centralized OAP and a network of spatially distributed LIoT nodes. Each node operates independently using harvested energy, while the OAP manages coordination, data aggregation, and serves as a gateway to external networks. Fig. 1 presents an overview of this architecture, detailing the primary functional blocks and their interactions within the energy-autonomous LIoT system [15–17].

3 Design Considerations and Implementation Challenges

In general, the design of LIoT systems needs to adhere to the key principles established in our previous work [15–17], including complementing EH architectures, low power OWC strategies, and sustainable component integration. Specifically, energy autonomy can be supported through Harvest-Store-Use

Figure 1: Proposed architecture for LIoT-ASP: LED luminaires function as OAPs with gateway connectivity to the broader network. The LIoT node integrates components for OWC, PV-EH, and battery-free operation. The use of compact and sustainable PE contributes to reduced form factor and improved sustainability.

(HSU) protocols in conjunction with multidirectional PV-EH systems, allowing efficient energy capture from ambient illumination regardless of spatial orientation. To ensure reliable communication in complex indoor environments, the use of multidirectional optical transceivers is essential, as they enable omnidirectional reception and help mitigate the limitations imposed by the directional nature of OWC in weak Line-of-Sight (LOS) scenarios. For energy buffering, the use of sustainable electrostatic storage elements, such as Electric Double-Layer Capacitors (EDLCs), which represent the most common class of supercapacitors, offers significant advantages including high cycle stability and reduced environmental impact [22]. Their wide operating temperature range, which is beneficial for applications spanning cold-chain logistics to warm indoor environments, ensures reliable performance of LIoT-ASP systems under varying ambient conditions. Communication can be implemented using single-carrier intensity modulation with direct detection (IM/DD) or similar low-complexity optical schemes suitable for ultra-low-power operation [15]. For low-power operation, it is essential to adopt a duty-cycled design where the node remains in a low-power sleep mode and transitions to the active state based on either a wake-up trigger from the OAP or a predefined duty cycle schedule. The structure of the LIoT node, comprising the Energy Harvesting Unit (EHU) and the Sensing, Processing, and Communication unit (SPCU), along with the OAP, which includes the main controller and communication interface, is illustrated in Fig. 2, as described in our previous work [15–17]. For LIoT-ASP, it is essential to consider the following discussed design approaches.

3.1 Sustaining Node Operation Under Variable Optical Energy Availability

Effective energy storage is a key design consideration in LIoT systems to support reliable operation during low or fluctuating indoor illumination. When determining the appropriate capacitance value C for the LIoT-ASP, several factors need to be considered to ensure continuous functionality. Depending on the operational context, LIoT-ASP nodes may need to maintain functionality during periods when ambient energy is unavailable, such as nighttime conditions when indoor lighting is turned off, or during transport scenarios where illumination may be minimal. In order to support uninterrupted operation, the energy storage unit needs to be capable of sustaining

Figure 2: LIoT design structures: (a) LIoT node architecture, (b) optical access point (OAP) architecture [16, 17].

the node's energy demands throughout these intervals. Furthermore, the supercapacitor is expected to deliver sufficient energy for high-demand events, such as sensing operations without causing energy depletion. These operational requirements establish the permissible voltage range for the supercapacitor, represented by $[V_{\text{Min}}, V_{\text{Max}}]$, over which energy is accumulated and utilized. In order to ensure reliable operation in the absence of PV-EH, the minimum required capacitance can be approximated as follows [23]:

$$C_{\text{Min}} \approx \frac{2 \left(\frac{E_{\text{Peak}}}{\eta_{\text{EHU},s}} + P_{\text{Leak}} T_{\text{Peak}} \right)}{V_{\text{Max}}^2 - V_{\text{Min}}^2}, \quad (1)$$

where, E_{Peak} denotes the maximum energy required by the node, $\eta_{\text{EHU},s}$ is the energy delivery efficiency from the storage element to the system, P_{Leak} is the leakage power associated with the supercapacitor, and T_{Peak} is the maximum duration over which this energy may be consumed. The energy availability condition for executing a sensing task at the i^{th} instance is formalized in (2). This expression ensures that the node has sufficient buffered energy to complete the sensing task without interruption [24]:

$$E_i^{\text{sens}} \leq \left(E_i^{\text{buf}} - E_i^{\text{oper}} \right)^+, \quad (2)$$

where, E_i^{sens} denotes the energy required to complete the sensing task, E_i^{buf} represents the total buffered energy stored in the supercapacitor at the time of task evaluation, and E_i^{oper} accounts for the baseline energy required to maintain essential node operation during the task window, such as MCU runtime and peripheral standby. This condition guarantees that the node does not initiate sensing unless there is a sufficient energy margin beyond its operational overhead. By enforcing this constraint, unnecessary power failures and repeated restarts of the same operation due to premature energy depletion are avoided.

In the context of LIoT-ASP systems, when a node is triggered by the OAP to perform sensing operations, it must meet the energy availability condition defined in (2), based on the buffered energy E^{buf} accumulated at that moment. This requirement ensures that the node has adequate energy to complete the task, thereby preventing repeated execution failures caused by energy outages [25]. In order to mitigate such disruptions, energy-aware control strategies should be employed to evaluate available energy prior to initiating tasks with high energy demand. The node can assess E^{buf} by monitoring supercapacitor voltage levels and making informed decisions on whether to proceed with or defer task execution [25]. If the energy level is insufficient, the node may enter a low-power sleep mode to harvest additional energy and resume operation only once the condition in (2) is fulfilled. This forms the basis for an intermittent sensing mechanism, where sensing activities are conducted only when sufficient energy is available [26, 27]. Intermittent execution strategies can generally be divided into two types: best-effort intermittent and soft-intermittent models [28]. In best-effort execution, the node powers on and begins executing tasks immediately after surpassing a predefined activation threshold. It continues operation until the available energy falls below a minimum level, resulting in an abrupt shutdown. On the other hand, the soft-intermittent model initiates task execution only when a target energy threshold is met and allocates a predefined energy budget to complete the task. Before the energy storage level drops below the critical threshold, the system proactively enters sleep mode to minimize power consumption, thereby accelerating energy accumulation from ongoing EH.

The energy dynamics of these two approaches are

Figure 3: Intermittent operation models: (a) Best-effort intermittent mode, where the node operates until energy drops below the turn-off threshold; (b) Soft intermittent mode, where the node performs tasks within a predefined energy budget and enters sleep mode before reaching the critical energy level.

illustrated in Fig. 3, based on models introduced in [28]. For SPCU architectures that rely on volatile memory, the soft-intermittent strategy offers significant advantages. In contrast to best-effort operation, which may lead to loss of execution state upon energy depletion, the soft-intermittent approach allows the system to preserve program states and runtime data by entering a controlled sleep state prior to energy exhaustion. This enhances system stability and responsiveness, particularly in applications that require consistent context retention across multiple power cycles. As a result, soft-intermittent execution is better suited for LIoT-ASP nodes where maintaining execution continuity is essential. To mitigate the risk of energy outages caused by storage depletion, particularly when the capacitor voltage V_{Cap} approaches the lower threshold V_{Min} , implementing energy-aware operational strategies becomes essential. Due to their high power density characteristics, supercapacitors inherently exhibit voltage fluctuations during load execution. Consequently, real-time monitoring of the capacitor voltage provides a practical and accurate method for estimating the energy available to the node. If the observed voltage is inadequate to support the execution of the desired task, the node can transition to a low-power state,

such as sleep mode, thereby conserving energy and accelerating accumulation from the energy harvester. Although selecting the storage capacitance based on (1) ensures that sufficient energy is available when the capacitor is fully charged, this condition is often not guaranteed in practical indoor environments with limited or inconsistent energy input. Under such conditions, voltage-based decision-making facilitates a smooth transition to intermittent operation modes rather than experiencing a complete operational outage. This strategy supports sustained system reliability and prolongs the operational availability of the LIoT node. A simplified voltage-threshold-based control mechanism is presented in Algorithm 1 to illustrate this approach. Facilitating coordination between the EHU and the SPCU under continuous energy inflow further enhances resilience, helping to minimize service interruptions and enabling adaptive intermittent operation for energy-constrained LIoT systems.

Algorithm 1 Energy availability check based on supercapacitor voltage thresholds

Require: V_{Cap} (current capacitor voltage), V_{Task} (min voltage required to execute the task), V_{Min} (min voltage threshold to maintain node functionality)

```

1:  $V_{Cap} \leftarrow \text{MeasureVoltage}()$ 
2: if  $V_{Cap} \geq V_{Task}$  then
3:   return true
4: else if  $V_{Cap} \geq V_{Min}$  then
5:    $\text{EnterSleepMode}(\text{short\_duration})$ 
6: else
7:    $\text{EnterSleepMode}(\text{long\_duration})$ 
8: end if
9: return false

```

3.2 Indoor eye friendly Optical Wireless Communication Under Energy Constraints

3.2.1 Low power OWC requirement

Consumer IR based OWC demonstrates robust performance in indoor environments, even under the presence of ambient noise and interference. The widespread use in remote control devices for short-range communication is primarily attributed to the simplicity, energy efficiency, and reliable operation of the technology [29]. These characteristics make consumer IR protocols particularly suitable for portable applications where devices must operate over long durations on limited energy budgets. In the context

of LLoT-ASP systems, the uplink typically involves the transmission of low-volume data, such as periodic sensor readings. This limited data requirement aligns well with the capabilities of consumer IR communication, making it a viable reference model for energy-aware uplink communication. In these protocols, the transmitter encodes a binary data stream into modulated optical pulses using an IR carrier wave, typically within the 30 to 60 kHz frequency range. The modulated signal is then transmitted using an IR LED emitter, while the receiver demodulates the incoming optical waveform to retrieve the original binary data [30]. Consumer IR systems generally employ Amplitude Shift Keying (ASK) for modulation, with data representation schemes including pulse distance, pulse width, pulse position, and Manchester encoding [29]. The data frame format in typical consumer IR protocols consists of a synchronization header, address bits, and a payload field. The address field allows directed communication between specific devices, while the payload carries commands or sensor data. Although OWC provides inherent physical layer security, vulnerabilities may exist at close proximity. In order to enhance data integrity and confidentiality, optional encryption and authentication mechanisms such as message integrity codes can be integrated, albeit with added computational complexity and longer frame lengths [30].

Several consumer IR standards are applicable to LLoT OWC design. For example, the RC-5 protocol utilizes Manchester encoding with a 36 kHz carrier and a concise 14-bit frame [31]. The NEC protocol employs Pulse Distance Encoding (PDE) with a 38 kHz carrier and supports a 32-bit frame structure [32]. Sony’s SIRC and Panasonic protocols implement pulse width and PDE, respectively, with carriers in the range of 38 to 40 kHz [33, 34]. These standards demonstrate reliable and energy-efficient operation in real-world indoor scenarios, providing proven frameworks for LLoT-ASP OWC implementations. Therefore, exploiting existing consumer IR communication protocols offers a practical and low-power solution for LLoT systems. Their minimal complexity, reliable performance under typical indoor lighting conditions, and compatibility with energy-constrained operation make them well-suited for the OWC requirements of LLoT-ASP applications.

3.2.2 Eye friendly downlink communication

Safe and visually comfortable lighting is a fundamental requirement in indoor VLC environments to ensure user well-being. The IEEE 802.15.7 standard addresses this requirement by incorporating dimming capabilities and ensuring flicker-free operation, even under low-dimming conditions [35, 36]. Flicker, characterized by rapid temporal changes in luminance, can adversely affect human perception and performance. In order to mitigate this, the standard introduces the concept of a Maximum Flicker Time Period (MFTP), within which brightness variations must be confined to remain imperceptible [36]. IEEE 802.15.7-2018 recommends the use of visibility patterns and idle pattern transmission to preserve constant illumination during non-communication (inter-frames) periods. Idle patterns may include in-band signals that are detectable by the receiver or out-of-band signals such as a steady DC bias [36]. Complementary to this, IEEE 1789 [37] outlines recommended practices for modulating high-brightness LEDs to mitigate health risks associated with temporal light modulation. The standard defines Percent Flicker (PF), a key metric in assessing visual comfort and safety, as follows:

$$PF = 100 \times \frac{L_{\max} - L_{\min}}{L_{\max} + L_{\min}}, \quad (3)$$

where L_{\max} and L_{\min} are the maximum and minimum light intensities, respectively. Since the luminous intensity of LEDs in their linear operating region is approximately proportional to the driving current [37], this expression can also be interpreted in terms of current modulation. The relationship between percent flicker and modulation frequency (f) is used to define safety thresholds, as summarized in Table 1.

In VLC-based LLoT systems, modulation depth directly influences the signal detectability at the receiver. Higher modulation depth enhances signal strength and improves the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), thereby lowering the minimum required optical power for successful communication [38]. In order to ensure robust communication in indoor settings, the modulation depth (m) should be optimized while considering transmission distance, path loss, and ambient light interference. The modulation depth is defined as [38]:

$$m = \frac{\Delta I}{I_0}, \quad (4)$$

Table 1: Percent Flicker Safety Limits Based on IEEE Std 1789-2015 Recommendations [37].

Limit Type	Condition	Purpose
NOEL (No Observable Effect Level)	$PF < 0.0333 \times f$	No observable effect; safe for all, including sensitive individuals.
Low-Risk Level	$PF < 0.08 \times f$	Low probability of adverse biological effects in the general population.
Seizure Threshold	$PF < 5\%$ for $f \geq 90$ Hz	Reduces risk of seizures in individuals with photosensitive epilepsy.

where I_0 is the LED bias current and ΔI is the amplitude of the modulated current signal.

4 Prototype Development

The primary aim of the developed prototype was to monitor the internal temperature of a container and transmit the acquired data to the end user. In addition to sensing functionality, the system supported downlink communication for dynamically updating information on integrated product displays, including parameters such as quality indicators and branding elements. During the component selection and design phase, priority was given to commercially available hardware that supports low-power operation and general-purpose energy-efficient performance.

The implemented LIoT node was equipped with a temperature sensor for monitoring ambient conditions. Sensor data was transmitted to the OAP via an IR-based uplink, while display updates were delivered through a visible light downlink channel. The prototype is illustrated in Fig. 4. The OAP was responsible for managing bidirectional communication with the node and was interfaced with the internet through a Wi-Fi module. This setup enabled real-time data transmission to a cloud-based service (ThingSpeak), allowing users to remotely monitor the container’s condition using any internet-enabled device. The graphical user interface for both the web-based dashboard is shown in Fig. 5.

4.1 LIoT-ASP: OAP Design

The OAP was developed using a commercially available table lamp housing and standard low-power components, as shown in Fig. 6. A USB-powered DC adapter was employed to supply power to the system, enabling a plug-and-play setup that simplifies on-site deployment and testing.

4.1.1 Main Controller: Processing Unit and LED Driver

The main controller unit integrates two MCU platforms for functional partitioning. A Raspberry Pi Pico with Wi-Fi support serves as the internet gateway, handling remote communication and user interface interaction. An Arduino Nano is used for signal-level processing, including data encoding and modulation for optical transmission, as well as reception and decoding of incoming signals. These two MCU communicate over a serial interface, enabling coordination of data transfer and control commands between the cloud platform and the LIoT node. For optical signal modulation, a Series Switch Modulator (SSM) configuration was implemented, following the approach outlined in [39]. The LED driving functionality was realized using an IRF520-based N-channel MOSFET module, which provided fast and energy-efficient current switching.

4.1.2 Communication Unit: Illumination Source and uplink Receiver

In order to ensure compatibility with both EH and human visual comfort, two types of phosphor-converted white LED arrays were evaluated as downlink transmitters: warm white (3000 K) and cool white (5000 K). These Chip-on-Board (COB) LEDs were directly driven using the modulated output from the SSM circuit. Fig. 7 presents the spectral power distributions of both LED types, measured under a standard indoor illumination level of 500 lux. The results indicate that cool white LEDs emit a broader short-wavelength spectrum, offering a higher photon energy density, which may benefit PV-EH performance. For uplink reception, an Optical Signal Detector (OSD) module based on the KY-022 IR receiver was integrated into the OAP. This module employs a TSOP1833 PIN photodiode with integrated amplification and filtering circuits to ensure robust detection of modulated infrared signals. The TTL-compatible output of the OSD was directly interfaced

Figure 4: Implemented PoC LIoT-ASP prototype for smart container applications in supermarket, retail, and storage environments: (a) Prototype LIoT-ASP OAP and node, (b) LIoT-ASP node, (c) Controllable printed-electronics-based display units for indicating product quality index and logo, (d) GUI displayed on a smartphone for wireless control of the OAP.

Figure 5: ThingSpeak-based web interface displaying transmitted temperature information accessible via the internet (ThingSpeak Dashboard).

Figure 6: Prototype implementation of the OAP incorporating the main controller and communication unit based on the proposed LIoT architecture.

with the Arduino Nano, facilitating efficient uplink data acquisition from the LIoT node.

4.1.3 OAP: Operating algorithm

The operating algorithm for the PoC OAP is outlined in Algorithm 2. In this implementation, the Raspberry Pi Pico MCU initially receives user commands via Wi-Fi. These commands are then forwarded to the Arduino Nano MCU, which handles communication with the LIoT node.

4.2 Optical Wireless Communication Protocol Design

In the developed PoC LIoT-ASP system, a consumer-grade IR communication protocol was employed for both uplink and downlink communication. This choice was driven by the availability of compact and energy-efficient monolithic ICs designed for IR-based communication, making them optimal for low-power and EH based IoT applications. For data encoding, PDE was utilized. By design, PDE maintains a fixed-duration bit mark, during which the optical transmitter emits a constant-length pulse. This approach minimizes power consumption by varying only the bit space duration, which typically keeps the transmitter in an off state between pulses. As a result, PDE is inherently compatible with the low power OWC. By adopting such protocols, the system design can be simplified, facilitating the energy-autonomous operation of the LIoT node. Moreover, the modest data rate requirements of the application scenario align well with the capabilities of these protocols. Additionally, the use of carrier-based modulation enhances robustness against ambient noise, making the system more resilient in complex indoor environments.

4.2.1 Physical Data Frame Structure

The communication protocol employed a custom 48-bit data frame structure, consisting of 16 address bits and 32 payload bits, designed to support bidirectional communication, scalability across multiple LIoT nodes, and interoperability with multiple OAPs. The data frame structure was implemented using the Arduino `IRremote` library (version 2.3) [40], which offers support for user-defined frame formats. The format of the implemented data frame is shown in Fig. 8. In the uplink direction (LIoT node to OAP), the 48-bit frame consists of 16 bits for the destination address, 8 bits for the source identifier (e.g., node ID), and 24 bits used to encode operational data. For downlink transmission (OAP to LIoT node), the payload similarly contains 16 destination bits and 8 source bits, while the remaining 24 bits are allocated for control instructions. These instructions including display update and sensor reading requests. In order to ensure synchronization and robust reception, each data frame was prefixed with a modulation header, following conventions used in consumer IR protocols. Although this lightweight structure imposes certain limitations on expandability and numerical precision, it offers a practical trade-off among

Figure 7: Spectral power distributions of warm white (3000 K) and cool white (5000 K) LEDs, measured using a spectrometer under 500 lx illumination.

Algorithm 2 Summary of LIoT-ASP OAP Operation

Require: Incoming WiFi command

- 1: **while** true **do**
- 2: WaitForWiFiCommand()
- 3: **if** WiFiDataReceived() == **true** **then**
- 4: **if** ChangeDisplayParameter() == **true** **then**
- 5: selector ← GetDisplaySelector()
- 6: SendDisplayChangeRequestToNode(selector)
- 7: **else if** TemperatureRequest() == **true** **then**
- 8: SendTemperatureRequestToNode()
- 9: WaitForUplinkResponseOrTimeout()
- 10: **end if**
- 11: **end if**
- 12: **end while**

communication reliability, energy efficiency, and ease of implementation. These characteristics are particularly important for battery-less LIIoT systems operating under constrained indoor conditions.

Figure 8: Communication data frame structure composed of address and payload sections. The 48-bit format includes destination address, source ID, and node-specific data.

4.3 LIIoT-ASP: Node Design

The implemented structure of the node is illustrated in Fig. 9a, comprising two primary subsystems: the EHU and the SPCU.

4.3.1 Energy Harvesting Unit

The EHU of the node was built around the EPISHINE EK01LEH development kit, which implements a HSU EH strategy. The EK01LEH integrates the AEM10941 power management integrated circuit, featuring Fixed Output Control Voltage (FOCV) based Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) and a dedicated cold-start functionality for low-input energy conditions. The onboard energy storage is provided by a CAP-XX GA230F supercapacitor, rated at 400 mF. Additionally, a TPS62740 step-down DC-DC converter from Texas Instruments was incorporated to provide regulated voltage to the load. In order to enable PV-EH, two LEH3 50x50 printed Organic PV (OPV) modules were connected in parallel and interfaced with the EK01LEH input. The AEM10941 regulated the OPV modules to operate near their maximum power point using its built-in FOCV MPPT configuration. According to manufacturer specifications [41], the OPV material exhibits power densities between 25 and 44 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ under ambient illumination conditions ranging from 600 to 1000 lux. With a combined active area of 22 cm^2 , the dual-module configuration can generate approximately 1.1 to 1.93 mW of electrical power, assuming an EH efficiency of approximately 90%, as typically achieved by inductor-based PMICs [42, 43]. In the power delivery sequence, the harvested energy is first directed to the supercapacitor for buffering. The

stored energy is then regulated by the DC-DC converter before being supplied to the SPCU, ensuring stable operation of the sensing, processing, and communication components within the LIIoT-ASP node.

4.3.2 Sensing, Processing, and Communication Unit

The SPCU of the prototype LIIoT node was built around an Arduino Pro Mini development board, configured to operate at a reduced clock frequency of 8 MHz and a regulated supply voltage of 3.3 V. This board is based on the Atmel ATmega328P microcontroller. In order to optimize for low-power operation, both the onboard status LED and integrated voltage regulators were disabled. Peripheral modules were powered through the GPIO lines of the MCU, allowing on-demand activation and deactivation to minimize standby power consumption. For LIIoT-ASP node inside temperature monitoring, a TMP36 low-power analog temperature sensor was integrated. The node also featured two electrochromic displays for visual feedback, primarily used to present downlink data from the OAP, such as quality indicators or identification tags. In order to monitor the energy buffer status, a voltage measurement circuit was implemented using an IRLML2402 MOSFET. This switch enabled a voltage divider to momentarily scale the supercapacitor voltage for sampling by the MCU’s Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC). Following the measurement, the MOSFET disconnects the voltage divider to prevent leakage and unnecessary energy loss, thereby preserving system-level energy efficiency. The probe circuit is illustrated in Fig. 9b. For uplink communication, the node employed a 3 mm IR LED driven by a 2N2222 NPN bipolar junction transistor to transmit data to the OAP using an infrared optical link. For downlink reception, a visible-light-compatible photodiode was coupled with a VSOP38338 preamplifier module. This integrated module features a narrowband band-pass filter and Automatic Gain Control (AGC), improving noise resilience and signal fidelity under ambient lighting interference. The analog output of the preamplifier was routed to the MCU’s ADC, where the sampled waveform was digitally processed and decoded to extract control information transmitted by the OAP.

4.3.3 Node Algorithm

By considering the PV-EH and consumption characteristics of the node, the operational algorithm is

Figure 9: Prototype implementation of the LIoT-ASP node: (a) Node structure comprising the EHU and SPCU modules, based on the proposed architecture. (b) Probe circuit employed for storage measurement to assess energy availability.

defined in Algorithm 2. The algorithm primarily alternates between standby, active, and sleep modes, each associated with different power consumption levels. In order to enable sleep mode functionality in the node, the Arduino AVR Low Power [44] library was utilized to manage the power states of the ATmega328P MCU. In the idle state, the node remains in standby mode, waiting for an external interrupt to occur. When a data frame header is received, or due to repeated transmissions of the same data frame, the transceiver circuit triggers an interrupt, waking the MCU from sleep and transitioning it to active mode for signal decoding. Once the signal is successfully decoded, the destination address is verified, after which the node executes the corresponding task based on the received command.

In this implementation, the *CheckEnergyAvailability()* function is driven by the algorithm presented in Algorithm 1, ensuring that the node does not experience energy shortage during task execution, which could otherwise lead to node outage until the turn-on energy threshold is reached again. After a successful interaction with the OAP, the node enters a short-duration sleep mode to facilitate rapid energy recovery following task execution.

5 Performance Evaluation

5.1 Node power consumption and energy autonomous operation

The measured power consumption profile of the prototype LIoT node, operating under the control of Algorithm 2, was obtained using the Nordic Power Profiler Kit and is illustrated in Fig. 10. Table 2 further

Algorithm 3 Summary of LIoT-ASP node operation

```

1: Input: User command through OAP
2: Output: Changing Display information and Sensor readings transmission
3: while Node is in "Standby mode" do
4:   if Wake-up trigger is detected then
5:     Transition to "Active mode" (turn ON core)
6:     Turn OFF transceiver
7:     Decode and interpret the OAP command
8:     if Destination address matches node ID then
9:       if CheckEnergyAvailability() == true then
10:        if Display update is requested then
11:          Update Display 1 and Display 2
12:        else if Temperature data acquisition is requested then
13:          Acquire data from TMP36 sensor
14:          Turn ON transceiver
15:          Encode and transmit data via IR uplink
16:        else
17:          Received command corrupted or unrecognizable; execution skipped
18:        end if
19:      end if
20:    else
21:      Address mismatch; return to standby mode
22:    end if
23:    Turn ON transceiver
24:    Transition to "Standby mode" (turn OFF core)
25:    Enter "Sleep mode" (short_duration)
26:  else
27:    Remain in "Standby mode"
28:  end if
29: end while

```

Figure 10: Power profile of the node corresponding to Algorithm 2, illustrating the standby, active, and sleep operating modes.

summarizes the operational states of the node along with the associated current consumption levels. During the sleep mode, the communication transceiver remains deactivated, rendering the node temporarily unresponsive to incoming signals from the OAP until it returns to either standby or active state. Analysis of the current values in Table 2 shows that during both sleep and standby conditions, the node functions in a net energy surplus regime, where the harvested energy exceeds the instantaneous consumption. This surplus is stored in the supercapacitor and later utilized during high-power consumption intervals, such as active sensing or data transmission, where the node demand exceeds the immediate supply from the harvester.

Table 2: Node Power Consumption in Different Modes.

Mode	Description	Current (μA)	Power (mW)
Sleep	MCU off, TX off	25.06	0.082
Standby	MCU off, TX on	359.32	1.186
Active	MCU on, TX on	4130.00	13.63

As previously outlined, the OPV-based EHU, comprising two OPV modules, is capable of fulfilling the node’s energy requirements during standby conditions. In these scenarios, the node remains powered

Figure 11: Bit rate variation as a function of bit mark duration in the PDE scheme used for communication.

and receptive to external events. This level of performance is sustained under illumination intensities starting at 600 lux, ensuring energy-neutral or positive operational states in the LIoT-ASP prototype implementation.

5.2 Low power uplink communication

In order to determine the optimum bit mark duration for PDE-based OWC, the impact on both bit rate performance and energy budget of energy-constrained LIoT nodes needs to be evaluated. The bit mark duration directly impacts the power consumption of the optical transmitter, as longer marks increase active transmission time, while shorter marks may affect signal detectability and timing accuracy. The bit space durations for logical '0' and '1' were fixed at 400 μs and 1200 μs . The relationship between bit rate and bit mark duration in the PDE scheme is depicted in Fig. 11. As illustrated in Fig. 11, the average bit rate decreases with increasing bit mark duration. This behavior is inherent to the structure of PDE, where each bit consists of a fixed-duration mark followed by a variable-duration space. Since logical '1' is represented by a longer space interval than logical '0', the achievable bit rate is bounded by the ratio of these symbols in the transmitted frame, with logical '0'-dominated frames yielding higher throughput.

In order to evaluate the communication performance of the proposed system, the Frame Delivery Ratio (FDR) is used as the primary metric. FDR is applicable for frame-based communication, where the successful reception of complete data frames is critical for application-level functionality. The FDR can be defined as follows:

Figure 12: Impact of bit mark duration on (a) frame delivery ratio (FDR), (b) transmission time per frame, (c) average transmit power per frame, and (d) average energy consumption per frame and per bit.

$$\text{FDR} = \frac{N_{\text{success}}}{N_{\text{total}}}, \quad (5)$$

where N_{success} is the number of successfully received data frames, and N_{total} is the total number of transmitted data frames.

Using FDR as the evaluation metric, the impact of bit mark duration on uplink communication performance and energy consumption was assessed by varying the bit mark duration. The results are presented in Fig. 12. Fig. 12a shows that the FDR improves with longer bit mark durations due to enhanced signal detectability at the OSD. A peak FDR of approximately 84% was recorded at a bit mark duration of 500 μs , whereas the lowest FDR, below 40%, occurred at 300 μs . Beyond 500 μs , a decline in FDR was observed, possibly due to hardware constraints such as the response time and demodulation capabilities of the receiver circuitry. Fig. 12b shows that total frame transmission time increases proportionally with bit mark duration. Similarly, Fig. 12c indicates that average transmit power per frame rises with longer bit marks, reflecting the extended drive duration of the optical source. This leads to higher total energy usage, as indicated in Fig. 12d, where both energy consumption per frame and energy per bit exhibit an increasing trend. These findings emphasize the trade-off between throughput, reliability, and energy efficiency. While a 500 μs bit mark duration achieves the highest FDR, it results in greater energy consumption and a lower bit rate compared to shorter durations. Therefore, selecting an optimal bit mark duration is essential for maintaining energy-autonomous operation, especially in systems with limited harvested energy. For the prototype implementation, a duration of 500 μs was selected as a compromise, offering reliable communication with a maximum achievable

bit rate of approximately 1.1 kbps. The full 48-bit data frame captured at this configuration is shown in Fig. 13.

Figure 13: Captured waveform of the communication protocol comprising a synchronization header and a 48-bit data frame using PDE. The bit mark duration is 500 μs , with bit space durations of 400 μs and 1200 μs representing logical '0' and '1', respectively.

5.3 VLC flicker free downlink communication

The temporal variation of the transmitted optical signal, determined by the envelope of the encoded and carrier-modulated waveform, plays a key role in potential flicker generation and must be considered in the system design. For the selected bit mark duration of 500 μs , the average envelope frequency for a 48-bit frame corresponds to approximately 850 Hz. Under typical IR communication schemes, this results in a flicker percentage of 100% as the LED transitions fully between on and off states. According to the IEEE 1789 guidelines summarized in Table 1, maintaining flicker levels below 28.3% is necessary for the NOEL, while levels below 68% are acceptable under the low-risk category for this frequency. In order to mitigate flicker and ensure compliance with

eye-safety requirements, an out-of-band idle pattern approach was employed by introducing a DC bias current to prevent the optical output from dropping to zero intensity. With a maximum output current of 1 A, the LED driver must maintain a minimum DC bias current of 0.717 A to meet the NOEL limit, or 0.32 A to comply with the low-risk threshold, based on the recalculated flicker limits for an 850 Hz envelope frequency. While this technique reduces perceptible flicker, it also decreases the modulation depth, as defined in (3), which may impact OSD sensitivity, particularly as a function of the optical path length between the OAP and the LIoT node.

In order to evaluate the performance of the consumer IR-inspired, flicker-free VLC downlink, the FDR was measured at varying heights using the same downlink receiver design implemented in the LIoT-ASP prototype. The experiment was then repeated under background illumination noise by introducing a constant 500 lux light source directed at the receiver surface to simulate the impact from neighbor light sources. As shown in Fig. 14, the downlink communication achieves an FDR exceeding 60% at distances up to 0.6 m, even in the presence of ambient illumination noise. These results demonstrate the robustness of the proposed VLC link under typical indoor conditions where the light source (acting as the OAP) is located in close proximity to the LIoT nodes. This configuration is particularly suitable for deployment scenarios such as integrated shelf systems or smart product displays in retail environments, where illumination sources are typically positioned near the monitored items.

Figure 14: Prototype system VLC downlink performance under background illumination and OAP-only lighting conditions.

5.4 Operational Analysis in a Real-World Application

In order to evaluate the performance of the implemented LIoT-ASP prototype system, the following experiment was conducted. Two dairy products were initially placed inside a refrigerator and subsequently stored within the smart container. Fig. 15a shows the LIoT-ASP node containing packaged butter slabs during the experimental setup. As certain dairy products, such as butter, are highly susceptible to psychrotrophic bacterial growth under temperature abuse conditions, with microbial activity accelerating significantly above 20°C [45], a warning threshold of 18°C was selected and configured using the ThingSpeak platform’s widget settings to enable early detection of thermal deviation. The LIoT-ASP node was then used to periodically monitor and record the internal temperature of the container. Fig. 16 illustrates the temperature variation captured by the LIoT-ASP node during autonomous operation, demonstrating its capability for continuous environmental sensing while operating solely on harvested energy. As shown in Fig. 15b, when the temperature reached 18°C, a warning notification was triggered and displayed on the user’s smartphone via the ThingView application, integrated with the ThingSpeak platform. The notification indicated a temperature breach using a red alert status.

Figure 15: Real-world application experiment: (a) Prototype LIoT-ASP node monitoring packaged dairy products inside the container. (b) Internet-connected smartphone terminal displaying a temperature warning (ThingView App).

This experimental validation demonstrates the reliable end-to-end operation of the proposed LIoT-ASP system, integrating energy-autonomous sensing, optical communication, and cloud-connected user interaction within a sustainable smart packaging framework. The results demonstrate the practical feasibility of the proposed sustainable active smart packaging solution under realistic application and operating

Figure 16: Measured and transmitted temperature variation of the LIoT-ASP container holding dairy products outside the refrigerator.

conditions.

6 Conclusion

This work presented the design, implementation, and evaluation of a sustainable smart packaging solution based on LIoT architecture, referred to as LIoT-ASP. The proposed system integrates battery-free energy-autonomous operation, low-power OWC, and real-time cloud connectivity into a compact and deployable form factor suitable for product condition monitoring. A complete PoC prototype was developed using commercial components, featuring a battery-free node with PV-EH and a dual-mode OAP that supports flicker-free illumination and bidirectional OWC. Experimental results verified the system’s ability to reliably communicate under varying indoor illumination conditions while maintaining compliance with flicker safety guidelines. The use of consumer-grade IR communication protocols and flicker-free VLC demonstrated compatibility with energy-constrained environments, achieving effective FDRs and efficient power utilization. Furthermore, the prototype was validated in a real-world use case involving perishable goods, where temperature deviations were successfully detected and reported via an internet-connected interface. While OWC inherently relies on LOS conditions, which may limit the applicability of the LIoT-ASP concept in scenarios involving occlusion or stacked items, the proposed system is well-suited for deployments where LOS is available, such as on retail shelves or open product displays. In such environments, LIoT-ASP can complement existing tech-

nologies, maximizing sustainability benefits through battery-free operation and energy-autonomous active sensing. These results highlight the practical feasibility of deploying LIoT-ASP systems in real-world applications, including smart packaging, retail monitoring, and cold-chain logistics. As future work, low-power, IoT-friendly OWC protocols can be further optimized to enhance communication robustness by incorporating lightweight error detection mechanisms such as Cyclic Redundancy Checks (CRC), parity bits, or checksums. Additionally, to mitigate challenges arising from non-LOS scenarios, the feasibility of using Optically Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (O-RIS) can be explored as a potential solution. Furthermore, the reliance on conventional electronic components can be reduced by utilizing existing PV cells for both EH and OWC reception, enabling a more compact and energy-efficient node architecture. To further improve integration and reduce hardware complexity, the EHU and the SPCU can be consolidated into a System-On-Chip (SoC) platform, enhancing overall system efficiency and compactness while further minimizing the use of conventional electronic components. In addition, developing a middleware management layer that interfaces between distributed LIoT-ASP nodes and facility-level control systems could enhance scalability, interoperability, and real-time decision-making. Such a layer would facilitate seamless integration of LIoT-ASP into existing cold chain and retail infrastructure, enabling dynamic optimization of operations based on LIoT-ASP insights. This can support energy-aware facility management, reduce operational costs such as electricity usage, and strengthen sustainability across the supply chain. Overall, the proposed LIoT-ASP design and framework presents a feasible and scalable approach to sustainable IoT system design, enabling battery-free, light-powered active monitoring through smart packaging. This approach reduces product waste, enhances supply chain visibility, and promotes environmentally responsible practices in next-generation IoT-enabled packaging and logistics applications.

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